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Qualitative Identification and Prevalence of Intestinal Parasites Associated With Exotic Chickens (*Gallus Gallus Domesticus*) Slaughtered In Abakpa-Nike Market, Enugu South-East Nigeria

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Abstract

The focus of the study was a qualitative identification and prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of all the exotic chickens slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria. The area of the study was Abakpa-Nike, Enugu, South-East Nigeria. A total of two hundred intestinal contents (samples) of exotic chickens slaughtered in the Abakpa-Nike market were used for the study. It comprised 100 intestinal contents (samples) from broilers and old layers respectively. Five assistants (slaughter table owners) were involved in collecting the samples. Direct smear, simple flotation and sedimentation methods were used to prepare the intestinal contents (samples) for microscopic examination for parasite eggs and oocysts. Direct microscopy was used to observe the samples for eggs and oocysts at 40-100× magnification. Intestinal parasites identified were nematodes and protozoa. Specifically, the nematodes identified were *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarum*. The protozoon identified as *Eimeria* spp. The researchers concluded that exotic chickens slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria were associated with intestinal parasites. The prevalence of intestinal parasites in the slaughtered exotic chickens was 60(30%). The prevalence of *Ascaridia galli*, *Heterakis gallinarum* and *Eimeria* spp were found to be 32(16%), 20(10%), and 8(4%), respectively. It was found that the prevalence of intestinal parasites was higher in broilers 32(32%) than in old layers 18(18%). Hence, the broilers are predisposed to intestinal parasite infection than the old layers. The researchers recommended that poultry farmers in Abakpa-Nike, Enugu State Nigeria should take adequate measures to control the parasites to avoid the consequences associated with the intestinal parasite infestation.

Keywords: Intestinal parasites, exotic chickens, broilers, old layers, prevalence, slaughter.

INTRODUCTION:

Protein is one of the nutrients required by the human body. It is essential for growth and maintenance, acts as a messenger in the body, an important structural component of cells and tissues, and regulates body processes, among others [1]. Health issues such as kwashiorkor and stunted growth in children, weak muscle tone, thin and bristle hair are associated with protein deficiency [2]. The recommendations of the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (UN) is that an average person should consume about 65g/day of protein, and 36g of it should come from animal protein [3]. Chicken is an animal delicacy for most Nigerian households, and it is predominantly eaten fried, cooked, roasted, or dried. Chickens, therefore, are sources of animal protein to most Nigerians. Yusuf [4] found out in a study that the demand for beef in Ibadan Metropolis, Nigeria is elastic, while the demand for chicken is inelastic. This implies that chicken is effectively demanded irrespective of the prevailing market price in Ibadan Metropolis, and this also applies in most cities in Nigeria.

Chicken (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) is an omnivorous bird [5] reared in most parts of the world, primarily for their meat and eggs. Chickens are the most popular poultry worldwide, and they are sources of meat and eggs [6]. Nigeria has the largest chicken production in Africa after South Africa and she has the largest egg production in Africa [7]. Commercialized intensive system and the traditional extensive or rural scavenging system are the two major poultry production systems [8]. In the traditional extensive system, chickens are left to scavenge in the daytime, and they obtain their food from the environment [9]. The rural

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poultry system is subsistence, village-based, or individual holding system, which is made up of stocks of non-standard breeds or mixed strains, types and ages and associated with little or no veterinary input [10]. On the other hand, the commercialized intensive system is capital and labour intensive and industrial in its prototype [10].

Chicken rearing is a fulltime or part-time business of some families in Abakpa-Nike, especially now that the governments lack the capacity to provide jobs to every qualified jobless person in Nigeria. Chicken rearing provides them with income to meet the family needs. Some families in Abakpa-Nike keep local chickens in their compounds, which they allow to roam about the surroundings and scavenge for food during the daytime. They are kept mostly for meat and may be sold in the market, especially when pressing need arises. More families keep exotic breeds which are reared in small cages or rooms, fed with feeds and water and rarely allowed to scavenge for food outside the cages or rooms. These family or household poultry farms carry birds of between ten and fifty in number. However, there are households that keep both the local and exotic breeds of chicken. A few large scales commercial poultry farms exist in Abakpa-Nike, which rear exotic chicken breeds as well as other birds in large numbers. Retailers buy these exotic chicken breeds from these large commercial poultry farms and resell them at the Abakpa-Nike market, which is a daily and a major market in Abakpa-Nike.

The parasite attack of chickens is a limiting factor in chicken production [8]. Parasites cause a reduction in growth and egg production in poultry, as well as the death of birds [11]. As a result, infection of parasites to chickens can lead to a very serious reduction in the amount of protein available to consumers such as consumers in Abakpa-Nike, Enugu, South-East Nigeria. The economically important intestinal parasites of poultry include nematodes (roundworms), cestodes (tapeworms), trematodes (flukes) and protozoa [12]. [13] identified *Ascaridia galli* (41.6%) (nematode), *Raillietina tetragona* (6.1%) (cestode) and *Emerica tenela* (3.9%) (protozoa) from the intestines of domestic chickens in Ikwuano, Abia State, Nigeria. Similarly, [14] identified *Ascaridia galli* (nematode), *Heterakis gallinarum* (nematode), *Choanotaenia infundibulum* (cestode), *Raillietina echinobothrida* (cestode) and *Prosthogominus* spp (trematode) from the gastrointestinal tract of slaughtered local chickens in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria, while [15] identified *Raillietina echinobothrida*, *R. tetragona*, *R. cestilus* and *Choanotaenia infundibulum* (cestodes) and *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarum* from the slaughtered chickens in Nsukka, South Eastern Nigeria. The purpose of the present study was a qualitative identification and prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with exotic chickens (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market Enugu, South-East Nigeria. To the best of the knowledge of the researchers and the relevant literature available to them, no such studies have been carried in Abakpa-Nike, Enugu, South-East Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Population of study

The population of the study comprises of all exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria.

Study area

The study was carried out in Abakpa-Nike, Enugu State, Nigeria. Abakpa-Nike is a suburban area located in the Enugu-East Local Government Area of Enugu, South-East Nigeria. Abakpa-Nike shares common climate conditions with Enugu, the capital city of Enugu State Nigeria. Enugu State is located in the tropical rainforest region of Nigeria, which is gradually being transformed into a derived savannah due to human activities such as urbanization and agricultural practices. The annual minimum and maximum temperatures are about 23.3⁰c and 32.5⁰c respectively. The annual rainfall is 1,757.2mm and the annual mean relative humidity at 0900GMT is 76.2%. Abakpa-Nike experiences dry and rainy seasons. The dry season starts from October to March, while the

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rainy season starts from March/April to September. The population of Abakpa-Nike is a mixed population comprising of strangers and Nike indigenes of diverse occupations such as crop and poultry farming, teachers, traders and artisans. There is one major market at Abakpa-Nike where different items are sold including chickens. A section of the market was designated for chicken sale. In this section of the market, broilers of age between two and four months and old layers of age one and above are sold. Broilers and old layers were identified by the researchers to be the only types of chicken sold in the Abakpa-Nike market at the time of conducting the research. This may be attributed to the fact broilers and old layers are usually the choice of families for meat. Meat to bone ratio in broilers is relatively small and as such they are reared primarily for meat production [16]. Layers are female chickens reared for egg-laying [17], and they are usually sold out for meat when their egg-laying has substantially dropped. Within the chicken sales area of the market were five slaughter tables whose owners slaughter and process chickens (broilers or old layers) for people who demand their services. It is from these slaughter tables that the samples (intestinal contents) were collected for the study.

Aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is a qualitative identification and prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with exotic chickens (*Gallus gallus domesticus*) slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria. The objectives of the study are:

- To determine the intestinal parasites associated with exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria.
- To determine the prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria.
- To determine the prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with broilers and old layers of exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the intestinal parasites associated with exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria?
2. What is the prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria?
3. What is the prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with broilers and old layers of exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria?

Methods of study

Sample collection

There were five slaughter tables identified by the researchers in the Abakpa-Nike market at the time of collecting the samples. The owners of the slaughter tables assisted in the collection of samples (intestinal contents). Before collecting the samples, the researchers educated the assistants (slaughter table owners) on the objectives of the study, the procedure for evacuating the intestinal contents from the intestines of the chickens slaughtered into clean bottles and the general precautions to take. Each of the five assistants was provided with a roll of thread, sixty clean 5ml screw-capped bottles, two packets of hand gloves and a cooling box. Thirty of the bottles provided for the assistants were labeled broiler and old layer respectively. The labeling was done to ensure correct placement and identification of the samples. The assistants wore the hand gloves on each occasion the samples were collected, and they were changed in-between collections to avoid contamination of samples with samples from other intestines. The portion between the intestine and the ventriculus (gizzard) of the alimentary tract of the slaughtered chickens were tied with thread to ensure that only the contents of the intestines were evacuated into the bottles. While holding the intestines longitudinally, the intestines were

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pressed carefully and gradually downwards, starting from the tied portion towards the cloacae until the intestinal contents were evacuated through the cloacae into the bottles already placed in position, and immediately screwed with a cap to avoid being contaminated with samples from other intestines. The bottles and their contents were immediately placed in the cooling boxes to avoid deterioration and larval development. Only the intestinal content from one broiler or old layer was placed in a particular bottle and care was taken not to mix them up. The cooling boxes and the samples were transported to the laboratory in each day of collection and the samples were taken out of the cooling boxes and placed in the refrigerator at a temperature of 4°C [8] waiting preparation and identification of parasites. The samples were placed in the refrigerator at the stated temperature to prevent spoilage and larval development from the eggs. The collections of samples were done on weekends (Saturdays and Sundays), which were the day's chickens were expected to be slaughtered in large numbers due to weekend celebrations. Samples were collected in four weekends (Saturdays and Sundays) between the months of July and August. The formular [18] below was used to calculate the sample size:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P (1-P)}{d^2}$$

Where n= sample size,

Z= Z statistic confidence level, 95% (1.96),

p= expected prevalence, 20% (0.2),

d= precision, 5% (0.05),

The expected sample size was 245, but only 200 samples (one hundred intestinal contents from broilers and old layers respectively) were collected during the period of collecting the samples. July and August in Nigeria are peak periods of the rainy season, which affected market operations, and this limited the number of exotic chickens slaughtered within the period. The preparation and examination of the samples for intestinal parasites lasted on an average of three days on each occasion.

Qualitative determination of intestinal parasites

The methods of direct smear, flotation and sedimentation were used to prepare the samples for microscopic examination as described by [8].

Direct smear

Direct smear was employed in the study because it can be used to identify helminth eggs and coccidian oocysts, and is used for animals that have been killed [8]. A small number of samples (intestinal content) were placed on a clean, grease-free slide. One drop (1cm³) of clean tap water was added to the sample on the slide and mixed using a glass stirring rod. A coverslip was placed on top of the slide and examined in a compound microscope using 40-100× magnification.

Flotation method

Flotation is the most widely used principle for concentrating parasite eggs [8]. Simple flotation was applied in preference to testing tube flotation because of the large surface area involved and the short distance the eggs had to travel. As helminth eggs and coccidian oocysts have specific gravities (relative density) that are lower than the plant residues in the intestinal contents, the eggs may be separated from the intestinal contents by mixing the intestinal content with a fluid in which the eggs will float above it, while the plant materials sink. The principal of flotation follows from the Archimedes Principle, which states that any object or body that is partially or wholly immersed in a fluid will experience an upward force that is equal to but opposite to the weight of the fluid that was displaced [19]. In order words, an object will float only if the object is less dense than the liquid in which it is placed [19]. The fluid used to float the eggs of the parasites was a saturated solution of sodium chloride (NaCl) and white sugar [8]. The saturated salt/sugar solution was used because its specific gravity

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(relative density) of 1.280 is higher than that of parasite eggs, and therefore, gives best results [8]. The saturated solution was prepared by measuring out 400g of common salt (NaCl) and 500g of white sugar using G & G electronic scale of 0.01g sensitivity. The salt was dissolved in 1000ml of clean tap water in a 2000ml capacity beaker and stirred with a glass rod until no more salt dissolved. Then the measured white sugar (500g) was added to the saturated salt solution and stirred with a glass rod until the sugar was dissolved.

Three grams (3g) of intestinal content were weighed out using G & G electronic scale and transferred into a 100ml beaker labeled 1. Fifty milliliters (50ml) of the flotation fluid was measured out with a 100ml measuring cylinder and poured into beaker 1, and the mixture (intestinal content and flotation fluid) were mixed thoroughly with a glass stirring rod. Immediately after stirring, the intestinal suspension was poured into a nylon tea strainer into a 100ml beaker labeled 2. The intestinal debris was discarded and the beaker 2 was left without being disturbed on the laboratory table for ten minutes, during which the eggs of the parasites float and accumulated in the surface layer. A clean, dry test tube was dipped down to the bottom of the intestinal suspension, and in one movement the test tube was carefully lifted out of the fluid. The drops of intestinal suspension that adhered to outer surfaces of the test tube were transferred to a slide. The bottom end of the test tube was made to rest on the slide for about two seconds for the drops to run off. A coverslip was placed on the microscope slide and the sample examined at 40-100× magnification in a microscope.

Sedimentation method

Eggs of trematodes have high specific gravities. Hence they do not float in common flotation fluids, but they may be concentrated by sedimentation [8]. The method of sedimentation, as applied in this study, makes use of the high specific gravity (relative density) of trematode eggs, which facilitated their sedimentation in beakers with steeply sloping sides. The process involves washing and sieving of intestinal contents to remove the smallest as well as the largest particles. Three grams (3g) of intestinal content was transferred to a 100ml beaker labeled 1. Fifty milliliters (50ml) of clean tap water were measured out with 100ml measuring cylinder and poured into beaker 1 and the mixture was thoroughly stirred with a glass stirring rod. The intestinal content was immediately poured into a nylon tea strainer into another 100ml beaker, and 10ml of it was measured out with a 100ml measuring cylinder and transferred into a test tube placed in a test tube rack. The intestinal particles and the trematode eggs were allowed to settle for a period of 10 minutes. After this period, the supernatant was carefully removed with a pipette and discarded, and care was taken not to re-suspend the sediment during the process. Clean tap water was added to the sediment in the test tube such that it is almost filled up in order to re-suspend. The test tube and the intestinal particles were left undisturbed for about 10 minutes to allow the trematode eggs to sediment. The supernatant was removed in one steady movement with a pipette, and care was taken not to re-suspend the sediment. One drop of methylene blue was added, which stained the intestinal particles blue. One drop of the stained sediment was taken with a dropping pipette to a microscope slide and examined at 40-100× magnification in a microscope. The last step was repeated until all the sediments were examined.

Identification of parasites

Intestinal parasites were identified by the characteristic appearances of the eggs and oocysts as described by [20] and [8].

Data analysis techniques

Data were presented in tables and analyzed by percentages. Prevalence was calculated by the relationship as described by [8]:

$$\text{Prevalence} = \frac{\text{Number of slaughtered chickens infected}}{100}$$

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 Total number of slaughtered chickens examined 1

RESULTS

Research question 1: What are the intestinal parasites associated with the exotic chickens slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria?

Table 1: Parasites associated with the exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria.

S/N	Name of Parasite	Class of Parasite
1	<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	Nematode
2	<i>Heterakis gallinarum</i>	Nematode
3	<i>Eimeria</i> spp	Protozoa

Table 1 shows that nematodes and protozoa are associated with the exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria. The nematodes identified were *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarium*, while the protozoa identified was *Eimeria* spp.

Research question 2: What is the prevalence of parasites associated with the intestinal contents of exotic chickens slaughtered in the Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria?

Table 2: Prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with the exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria.

S/N	Name of Parasite	Class of Parasite	Prevalence
1	<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	Nematode	32(16%)
2	<i>Heterakis gallinarium</i>	Nematode	20(10%)
3	<i>Eimeria</i> spp	Protozoa	8(4%)
Total			60(30%)

Table 2 shows that 8(16%) of the slaughtered exotic chicken breeds examined were positive for *Ascaridia galli*, 5(10%) were positive for *Heterakis gallinarium* and 2(4%) were positive for *Eimeria* spp. The table also shows that 15(30%) of the slaughtered exotic chicken breeds examined were positive for intestinal parasites.

Research question 3: What is the prevalence of intestinal parasites associated with broilers and old layers slaughtered in the Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu, South-East Nigeria?

S/N	Name of Parasite	Broiler	Old Layer	Total
1	<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	20(20%)	12(12%)	32(16%)
2	<i>Heterakis gallinarium</i>	12(12%)	8(8%)	20(10%)
3	<i>Eimeria</i> spp	0(0%)	8(8%)	8(4%)
Total		32(32%)	18(18%)	60(30%)

Table 3 shows 20(20%) of the examined slaughtered exotic breeds of broilers and 12(12%) old layers respectively were positive for *A. galli*, while 12(12%) slaughtered broilers and 8(8%) old layers were positive for *H. gallinarium*. *Emeria* spp was not identified in the slaughtered broilers but identified in the slaughtered old layers with a prevalence of 8(4%). The table also shows that 32(32%) and 18(18%) of the slaughtered broilers and old layers respectively were positive for intestinal parasites, making a total prevalence of 60(30%).

DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 1, nematodes and protozoa were identified in the exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in the Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu South-East Nigeria. The nematodes identified include *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarum*, while the protozoa identified as *Eimeria* spp. The observation in the present study is

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similar to the results obtained by [13] and [14]. The implication of the observation is that the *A. galli*, *H. gallinarum* and *Eimeria* spp infected chickens slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike, Enugu South-East Nigeria.

It was shown in Table 2 that the prevalence of intestinal parasites in the exotic chicken breeds slaughtered in the Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu South-East Nigeria is 60(30%). The prevalence of *Ascaridia galli*, *Heterakis gallinarum* and *Eimeria* spp were also given as 32(16%), 20(10%) and 8(4%) for *A. galli*, *H. gallinarum* and *Eimeria* spp respectively. These findings are different from the findings of [21] who found out that *Ascaridia* spp, *Heterakis* spp and *Eimeria* spp had a prevalence of 36%, 12.6% and 34.5% respectively in slaughtered local and exotic breeds of chicken reared in Gwagwalada area council. The difference may be due to differences in the sample size between the present study (200), and that by Jegede et al. (280).

Table 3 showed that the total prevalence of intestinal parasites in the slaughtered exotic chicken breeds of broilers and old layers in the Abakpa-Nike market, Enugu South-East Nigeria were 32(32%) and 18(18%) respectively. The result implies that the prevalence of intestinal parasites in broilers is higher than in old layers. Table 3 also indicated that there is a difference between the prevalence of *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarum* in broilers than in the old layers, in that they are higher in broilers than in the old layers. The prevalence differences in nematode infection between the broilers and layers might be attributed to age differences; in older fowls (such as old layers), the larvae of nematodes may undergo little or no development [22]. The prevalence of *Eimeria* spp in the broilers is 0(0%), while it is 8(8%) in the old layers. *Eimeria* spp is common wherever chicken is raised [12].

Chickens infested with a large number of nematodes suffer from blood loss, reduced blood sugar, and retarded growth, a decrease in egg production, diarrhea, and mortality [8]. In heavy infestations, *Ascaridia galli* can cause partial or total obstruction of the duodenum or the jejunum [8]. In addition, *Heterakis gallinarum* (caecal worm) causes inflammation and thickening of the caecal walls [22]. On the other hand, *Eimeria* causes coccidiosis that affects the caecum and intestines of birds [23]. *Eimeria* infections in chickens cause decreased growth, diarrhea and high mortality [8].

CONCLUSION

Chickens slaughtered in the Abakpa-Nike market are infected with intestinal parasites and their prevalence is not negligible. Healthy birds are necessary for success in poultry farming. Unhealthy birds lead to losses of money in terms of death and the cost of treatment. Losses due to death are obvious, but greater losses are associated with decrease in growth, egg and meat production among the birds. Therefore, since chickens' slaughtered in Abakpa-Nike market come from poultry farmers in Abakpa-Nike, Enugu South-East Nigeria, they should be the needful to control the parasites identified in the study.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the observations of the study, the researchers recommend that chicken farmers in Abakpa-Nike, Enugu South-East Nigeria should take necessary measures to keep intestinal parasites away and out of their chickens.

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REFERENCES

- i. Walle, G.V.D. (2018). 9 important functions of protein in your body. Healthline. Retrieved from <https://www.healthline.com>
- ii. Braizier, Y. (218). How much protein does a person need? MedicalNewsToday. Retrieved from www.medicalnewstoday.com

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- iii. Yusuf, T. M., Tihamiyu, S. A. & Aliu, R. O. (2016). *Financial analysis of poultry production in Kwara State, Nigeria*. *Africa Journal of Agricultural Production*, 11(8), 718-723.
- iv. Yusuf, O. E. S. (2012). *A system analysis of the demand for animal protein in rural and urban Nigeria: A case study of Ibadan Metropolis*. *JORIND*, 10(2), 208-213.
- v. Klasing, K. C. (2005). *Poultry nutrition: A comparative approach*. *J. Appl. Res.*, 14, 114-436.
- vi. Al-Nasser, A., Al-Khalifa, H., Al-Saffer, A., Khalil, F., Al-Bahouf, M., Ragheb, G, Al-Haddad, A. & Magshaly, M. (2007). *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 63, 285-300.
- vii. Sahel Capital (2015). *An assessment of Nigerian poultry sector (vol. 1)*. Sahel Capital Partners.
- viii. Permin, A. & Hansen, J. W. (1998). *Epidemiology, diagnosis and control of poultry parasites*. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, 1-169.
- ix. Njue, S. W., Ksiiti, J. L., Gusheru, S. G. & Mbugua (2001). *A survey of the disease status of village chicken in Kenya livestock, community and environment*. *Proceedings of the 10th conference of the association of Institutions of Tropical Veterinary Medicine, Copenhagen Denmark*.
- x. Adene, D. F. & Oguntade, A. E. (2006). *The structure and importance of the commercial and village-based poultry systems in Nigeria*. *FAO*, 1-110.
- xi. Whitmarsh, S. (1997). *Parasitic diseases (internal)*. *Poultry Science*.
- xii. MacDougald, L. R.(2008). *Internal parasites*. In Y. M.Saif et al. (eds). *Diseases of Poultry (1st ed.)*. Blackwell, 1056-1062.
- xiii. Ohaeri, C. C. & (2013). *Helminthic parasites of domestic fowls in Ikwuano, Abia State Nigeria*. *Journal of Natural Sciences*, 3(11), 1-5.
- xiv. Uhuro, A. C., Okafor, F. C., Odikammnor, O. O., Onwe, C. S., Abarika, M. C. & Elom, J. N. (2013). *Common gastrointestinal parasites of local chicken (gallus domesticus) slaughtered in some select eatry center in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State: Implication for meat quality*. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 2(2), 1416-1422.
- xv. Idika, I. K., Obi, C. F., Eze, I. O., Iheagwa, C. N., Njoku, I. N. & Nwosu, C. O. (2016). *Gastrointestinal helminth parasites of local chickens from selected communities in Nsukka region of South Eadt Nigeria*. *J. Parasit Dis.*, 40(4), 1376-1380.
- xvi. FoodNetwork (2016). *Chicken*. Retrieved from <http://www.foodnetwork.com/topics/chicken.html>
- xvii. Jacobs, R. D., Hogsette, J. A. & Butcher, G. D. (2015). *Nematode Parasites of Poultry*. University of Florida: Institute of Food and Agricultural Services, IFAS.
- xviii. Pourseinghholi, M. A., Vahedi, A., & Rahinzadeh, M. (2013). *Sample size calculation in medical studies*. *Gastroentorology and Hepatology From Bed to Bench*, 1-4.
- xix. Bormashenko, E. (2015). *Surface tension supported floating of heavy objects: Why elongated bodies float better?* *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 463(2016), 8-12.
- xx. Soulsby, E. J. I. (1982). *Helminths, Arthropods and Protozoa of Domestic Animals*. Bailliere Tindal publishers, 782-792.
- xxi. Jegede, O. C., Asadu, I. A., Opara, M., Obete, S. S. & Olayemi, D. O. (2015). *Gastrointestinal parasitism in local and exotic breeds of chickens reared in Gwagwalada guinea savannah zone of Nigeria*. *Sokoto Journal of Veterinary Sciences*, 13(3), 25-30.
- xxii. Saif, Y. M., Faldy, A. M., Glisson, J. R., Macgougald, L. R., Nolan, L. K. & Swayn, D. E. (eds.). (2008). *Diseases of Poultry (1st ed.)*. Blackwell, 1056-1062.
- xxiii. Singh, L. J. & Meitei, N. M. (2015). *Prevalence and intensity of infection of different Eimeria species in broiler chicken, Gallus gallus domesticus, from Imphal Manipur, India*. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 5(4), 817-819.